

Entropy and Classical Mechanical Considerations

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 4, 2022

Classical statistical mechanics seems to focus on the variables x and p (momentum) which create phase space. Classical mechanics also uses these two variables x , $p=mv$ (nonrelativistic), but is deterministic i.e. $x(t)$ and $v(t)$. If one considers a classical bound system and equal Δt time slices with a t value at the center, then one has t , $x(t)$ and $v(t)$, but also a varying Δx and Δv for each t . There is an uncertainty in t of Δt , but Δt is the same for each t . Thus for a given t , its real value is within $\{t-\Delta t, t+\Delta t\}$. Similarly there is a $\{x(t)-\Delta x(t), x(t)+\Delta x(t)\}$ and a similar expression for $v(t)$. If one assumes determinism for a given t_1 , the picking a t from within $\{t_1-\Delta t, t_1+\Delta t\}$ leads to a unique $x(t_1)$ and $v(t_1)$.

If on the other hand, one considers phase space and assumes a constant probability distribution for Δx and Δv i.e. assumes that their errors are not linked to the t_1 picked from $\{t_1-\Delta t, t_1+\Delta t\}$, then each t is associated with a number of possible states of $\Delta x \Delta v$ which is proportional to $F(x) \Delta x$ i.e. work. We try to examine this idea.

Next we consider a classical ideal gas with all particles moving with the same constant velocity i.e. no stochastic feature breaking the deterministic $x=vt$. This seems to lead to a conveyor belt type of equilibrium, but any small error in motion becomes magnified in time and destroys the equilibrium as there is no correction mechanism. (Note: at the walls of the box the particle reflects i.e. $v_{in} = -v_{out}$). For an initial Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution with constant spatial density, but only reflections and no inter-particle collisions, different speeds of particles destroys the MB distribution locally. As a result, it seems that stochastic two body collisions are needed to establish a statistical mechanical classical gas. The deterministic form $x=vt$ leads to disruptions in equilibrium we argue.

Classical Bound Particle

In this section we examine the possibility of phase space uncertainties for a classical bound particle. As an aside, we note that in (1) a quantum spatial entropy is defined by $-\int dx W_n(x) \ln[W_n(x)]$ and in the high energy limit ($n \rightarrow \infty$) it is compared with a classical calculation $-\int dx C/v \ln(C/v)$ where $v(x) = \text{classical velocity}$ from $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ and C is a normalization constant. Here $C/v(x)$ is proportional to Δt with Δx being constant i.e. the bound region is broken into equal Δx pieces. In other words, Δt is considered to be an uncertainty or probability (i.e. the amount of time a particle spends in a constant Δx). " Δt " varies with constant Δx . Here we consider Δt as being constant and consider fluctuations in $\Delta x(t)$ and $\Delta v(t)$.

For a particle moving with constant velocity $v = x/t$. For an accelerating bound particle there is a force $-dV(x)/dx$ where $V(x)$ is the potential. This seems to lead to a picture of small Δt , Δx and Δv regions. The assumption of classical mechanics is that for a tiny region Δx one has a constant $v(x)$ to first order i.e. $\Delta x = v(t) \Delta t$. The force or potential must act within the tiny Δx and Δt to change $v(x(t))$ to $v(x)+\Delta v(t)$. Even though the force appears to be deterministic in a coarse

grained picture (i.e. one does not see what happens within dx, dt) we try to consider a statistical scenario within this region. If one breaks time into equal dt slices then each t is associated with the same dt , but different $dx(t)$ and $dv(t)$ values i.e. one assumes fluctuations of x and v are independent of t during dt . If one has a constant probability distribution for each then the number of internal combinations within a dt is:

$$dx(t) dv(t) = dx(t) \frac{1}{m} F(x) dt \quad ((1)) \quad \text{using Newton's second law}$$

One may note that $F(x)dx$ is work and dt is a constant.

In other words, there is a varying phase space element for each dt slice even though dt is always constant.

For a given time slice, dt indicates the possible error in t . " dt " is constant for all t . The real value of t is within $A = \{ t-dt, t+dt \}$ with a constant probability distribution (chosen as an example). One may then calculate corresponding $x(t)$ and $v(t)$ values so these lie within $\{ x(t)-dx(t), x(t)+dx(t) \}$ and $\{ v(t)-dv(t), v(t)+dv(t) \}$. If one considers a t_1 chosen from $\{t-dt, t+dt\}$ as mapping into a specific $x(t) + dx_1(t)$ and $v(t)+dv_1(t)$ then each point in A maps into a specific " x " and " t " value or specific phase point and so the only uncertainty is in dt for each t . In such a case one does not make use of ((1)) and there is equal uncertainty at each t . This would be analogous to a kind of "isentropic" reversible motion for bound motion.

If on the other hand, one assumes ((1)) i.e. that one may have independent fluctuations in t , x and v with $dx(t)$ and $dv(t)$ being constrained by average motion, then ((1)) with the assumption of a constant probability distribution for x and v yields an entropy about t, x and v of $\ln(dt dx dv F(x) v)$ where $F(x)v$ is power and dt is constant. In ((1)) $F(x)dx$ is work. If one takes this view, it should be noted that a new equilibrium is established at each t , $x(t)$, $v(t)$ equilibrium points. For example, x cannot deviate by $dx_1 \max$ at t_1 and continue to deviate again in the next dt region etc because one would then observe nonclassical motion i.e. deviations from $x=vt$ in after many intervals. It is almost as if the force knocks the particle out of equilibrium, but then it settles down again such that $x_{ave}=v_{ave} t_{ave}$, but with x, t and v have random portions within $\{x-dx, x+dx\}$, $\{t-dt, t+dt\}$ and $\{v-dv, v+dv\}$ although dx and dv are constrained by average behaviour i.e. $dx = v_{ave}(t) dt$ and $dv = F(x_{ave}) dt/m$. Each dt slice, however, then has different "entropy" in terms of $\ln(dx dv)$ and one may go from high entropy in one dt region to lower entropy in the next although it may be noted that work is done.

Motion in a Classical Gas

In the above section we discussed possible uncertainties in a classical bound particle's trajectory. Here we wish to consider a collection of particles which move at constant velocity. Imagine a box with particles of the same magnitude of velocity, but pair forward and backward moving particles at equally spaced intervals. In such a case, if one has resolution only at the level of the spacing one would see equal density and no change in time. Also assume that the particle hitting the wall reflects with the same velocity. This is like a conveyor belt scenario. The problem is that if one introduces small errors in the motion of some of the particles it seems that

there is no way for these to be corrected. These errors will grow in time and upset the constant density, so it seems this is not a stable equilibrium.

Next, consider particles with velocities distributed according to the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution $P(v) = C \exp(-.5mv^2)$ and placed so spatial density is constant.

Assume reflection at the walls ($v_{in}=v_{out}$). At time "to" one may open a small hole in the wall and observe the MB distribution. Once these few particles are out, they must be replaced by incoming ones which should maintain the MB distribution, but they cannot because fast particles reach the wall before slow ones. This difference in speed disrupts the momentum distribution at any point. (Note there are not interparticle collisions and only reflection at the walls.)

Thus it seems that to have equilibrium stochastic collisions are required. In other words a statistical system is not based on deterministic motion $x=vt$, but rather on stochastic collisions. Even in classical mechanics there are stochastic collisions between two balls if one only considers the center of mass and overall momentum. Billiard balls may strike at different angles which affects the collision result. If collisions are stochastic then x and p become stochastic. In between collisions, however, the particle is deterministic i.e. $x=vt$.

Dilute Gas and Issues

This may lead to issues for a dilute gas. Consider a gas in which there are only collisions with the wall. These are no longer reflections ($v_{in}=v_{out}$), but collision outcomes are distributed according to the MB distribution because the wall is at temperature T . Deterministic motion within the box seems to disrupt equilibrium especially if the box is large because slow particles and fast particles travel different lengths in a time Δt . If one considers a dense gas then it does not matter that a slow particle needs to travel a long time before reaching a wall. It will receive a stochastic hit before this from another particle. If it reaches the wall, it receives a stochastic hit from it.

For the dilute gas this is not the case. Imagine at time "to" one places an MB distributed dilute gas with temperature T into the box. The fast particles hit the walls quickly and transfer some energy through collisions because they have more average energy than $constant \cdot T$. Normally this energy would be transferred by the walls back to the slow particles, but if they are late in arriving because the box is large, the box may dissipate some heat to the environment (assuming it is not isolated). Later slow and fast particles arrive, but the average temperature of these is lower than $constant \cdot T$ and so there should be a transfer of energy from the walls back. Thus there might be a very small periodic change in temperature with time in such a system. As a result it is not an ideal gas or in equilibrium. Thus it seems that rapid two body collisions are needed to ensure stochasticity in the system. This stochastic, however, leads to equilibrium i.e. stability. If there are small fluctuations within the system, it may self correct to maintain equilibrium. Thus, the so-called randomness or disorder of the stochastic hits or the system with an MB distribution (i.e. maximum entropy) actually represents stability (which is order in a certain sense). (For example, there is constant spatial density, temperature and pressure and one may create sound waves within which are ordered.)

Entropy Considerations

In the above scenario of the dilute gas, it seems that one does not have an equilibrium situation as there are heat flows at different times and different distributions governing different sets of the particles. For example the fast set of particles hitting the wall only represent the tail of the MB distribution, but these transfer energy to the wall to appear more like an overall MB distribution with lower energy. Later when the slow particles arrive with some fast ones, the wall again does not see an MB distribution and so tries to transfer energy to make the distribution more MB like. As a result, the entropy should not be maximized as in the MB case. This, however, suggests that the dilute gas is not in equilibrium.

References

1. Majernick, V. and Opatrny, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations for a quantum oscillator
Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and General 1999 29(9) 2197
DOI:[10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029](https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator